

Palm Tree Resort and Hotel Subic Bay: Accommodations

ACCOMMODATIONS

"We're more than accommodating."

[Palm Tree Resort](#) offers sea view rooms and suites, designed from the ground up with guest comfort in mind. Each room is exquisite, featuring individual ventilation units, king size beds, sofas, spacious bathrooms, widescreen television, DVD/CD players, high-speed internet access and reading chairs. All maximize the spectacular views of the sea and surrounding mountains, while providing guests with an upscale residential atmosphere.

All rooms include mini-bars, coffee makers, hairdryers, robes (Suites), complete bathroom amenities. Most rooms include high-speed Internet access.

London Suite

For the ultimate Palm Tree Resort experience this especially designed room, that inspires it's beauty & connects you with the surrounding environment, it has 1 bedroom suite, a large sunken living area with a cozy look and floor to ceiling picture windows that open onto a private balcony. Our signature bed features a pillow-top mattress, luxurious fine linens and duvets with down pillows. Enjoy a unique bathroom complete with beautiful vanity sink, European shower. Room amenities include cotton robes, luxury toiletries, hair dryer, in-room safe, 21" flat screen TV, DVD/CD Player, Cable, Clock/Radio, newspaper, wireless internet access and complimentary coffee & tea. As have all the added touches and ensures your comfort and convenience, you feel thoroughly at home and completely at your best.

Devon Suite

This Signature room offers one king size bed, a large sunken living area with window overlooking the garden. Our signature bed features a pillow-top mattress, luxurious fine linens and duvets with down pillows. Enjoy a separate bath from dressing area complete with beautiful vanity sink, European shower, Room Amenities include cotton robes, luxury toiletries, hair dryer, in-room safe, 21" flat screen TV, Clock/Radio, newspaper, wireless internet access and complimentary coffee & tea.

Deluxe Pool View Rooms

These rooms provide access to swimming pool & beach with a few steps from your room; where you can sit & sip cocktail at our poolbar, or soak up the sun in the beach. Our signature bed features a pillow-top mattress, luxurious fine linens with down pillows. Enjoy a Unique bathroom design complete with vanity sink, European shower. Room Amenities include luxury toiletries, hair dryers, in-room safe, 21" TV, cable, Clock/Radio, newspaper, mini bar, wireless internet access and complimentary coffee & tea.

Deluxe Mountain View and Sea View Rooms

These rooms offer you a King size Bed, with floor to ceiling picture windows that open onto a private balcony with mountain views or sea view. Our signature bed features a pillow-top mattress, luxurious fine linens with down pillows. Enjoy a Unique bathroom design complete with vanity sink, European shower. Room Amenities include luxury toiletries, hair dryers, in-room safe, 21" TVs, cable, Clock/Radio, newspaper, mini bar, wireless internet access and complimentary coffee & tea.

Deluxe Garden View Room

This room offers you a King size Bed, with windows facing a garden. Our signature bed features a pillow-top mattress, luxurious fine linens with down pillows. Enjoy a Unique bathroom design complete with vanity sink, European shower. Room Amenities include luxury toiletries, hair dryers, in-room safe, 21" TV, cable, Clock/Radio, newspaper, mini bar, wireless internet access and complimentary coffee & tea.

Deluxe Mountain View and Limited Sea View

These rooms offers you a King size Bed, with windows facing a mountain view sight and limited sea view. Our signature bed features a pillow-top mattress, luxurious fine linens with down pillows. Enjoy a Unique bathroom design complete with vanity sink, European shower. Room Amenities include luxury toiletries, hair dryers, in-room safe, 21" TV, cable, Clock/Radio, newspaper, mini bar, wireless internet access and complimentary coffee & tea.

Standard Room

Comfortable, well appointed room with a sea view and an access to a sharing Balcony. These serve the needs of guests who appreciate the value of a full-service resort at a minimum rate. Room Amenities include a queen size bed, wireless internet access, luxury toiletries, hair dryer, 21" TVs, Cable, in-room safe, Clock/Radio and complimentary coffee & tea.